

The Influence of The Saviter Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Subtema 3 Ways to Maintain The Health of Human Blood Circulation Organs in Class V Sdn 091608 Sinaksak T.A 2023/2024

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ABSTRACT

Savi learning model on student learning outcomes in subtheme 3 ways to maintain the health of human circulatory organs in class V SDN 091608 Sinaksak T.A 2023/2024. The type of research in this research is quantitative, the research population is all class V students at SDN 091608 Sinaksak totaling 30 students. The sampling technique used saturated samples, the sample in this study consisted of all class V of SDN 091608 Sinaksak, totaling 30 students. The research results show that student learning outcomes using the Savi model are in the good category with an average of 77.6. The results of the t distribution test are at a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) and $dk = N-1=30-1=29$, namely $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$, so the t distribution data with results is $18.525 > t \text{ table } 2.045$, so it can be said that there is a significant influence. The results of the t test table prove that there is an influence of the Savi learning model (x) on learning outcomes (Y) with the results of r calculated $> r \text{ table}$ with the results of t calculated $> t \text{ table } 18.525 > 2.045$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This proves that there is a significant influence from the use of the Savi learning model on student learning outcomes in sub-theme 3 ways to maintain the health of human circulatory organs in class V SDN 091608 Sinaksak T.A 2023/2024.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a factor in the process of life and development of a nation and state. Education is a vehicle for improving and developing abilities and forming the character and civilization of a nation that is useful in order to educate the nation's life, aiming to increase the potential of students to become human beings who believe in and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens. Therefore, education must be truly guided to create human beings with quality and noble character. Education is not just a transfer of knowledge between teachers and students, but education must also be used as a vehicle for moral development. In Law No. 20 of 2010 concerning the National Education System, it is stated that education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, morals, noble, as well as the skills necessary for himself, the people of the nation and the state.

Based on the results of observations at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar, the learning carried out by teachers tends to be passive because they still use conventional learning models. Where this learning model is still centered on the teacher who plays more of a role in the learning process while students only listen and record any information. In implementing the learning process, teachers only use one book as a learning resource which results in a lack of variety to attract students' attention in their desire to learn so that the learning that is being carried out is less effective so that students do not understand the learning material which has an impact on low student learning outcomes. It can be seen that the completeness of learning outcomes at SD Negeri No. 125138 Pematang Siantar has a KKM of 70. Daily test scores for class V students at SD Negeri No. 125138 Pematang Siantar, the total number of students is 38 students and those who meet the KKM are only 14 students, while the students who are below the KKM are 24 students so it can be concluded that the learning outcomes of class V students at State Elementary School No. 125138 Pematangsiantar is still low. To overcome this problem, a new innovation is needed in learning activities, one of which is using a learning model that can make students play an active role in learning activities, not feel bored, fed up and enthusiastic about achieving maximum learning results. Therefore, teachers must be clever in choosing learning models and adapting them to the learning material that will be delivered. The learning model that is considered capable of solving this problem is the student teams achievement division learning model. Learning model Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) is a cooperative learning model that encourages student cooperation through learning in groups with diverse members to master the skills being studied. Learning model Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) is very helpful for teachers to teach social skills to students. In this way, students can share knowledge with their group of friends who have been shared by the teacher, so that this can influence good student learning outcomes. This is what underlies the researcher's desire to carry out research at the school.

This is in accordance with the results of research conducted by Eduard F. Sidabutar, Minar Lumban Tobing, Lasma Siagian entitled "The Influence of the Student Team Achievement Division Type Cooperative Learning Model on Learning Outcomes in the Energy Benefits Sub-Theme in Class IV of SD Negeri 096113 Tanjung Saribu FY 2022/2023". This is proven by the fact that the average student score before using the student teams achievement division learning model was 47.33 and after using the student teams achievement division model it was 81.83. Apart from improving learning outcomes for the "Benefits of Energy" sub-theme, the student teams achievement division learning model can also increase students' interest in learning, so that students become more active in learning, learning also becomes easier, and more fun for students because the student teams achievement division learning model makes it easier for students in understanding the lesson. From the results of the research data normality test, the research class significant value was 0.561, which means it has a normal distribution. The results of the hypothesis test (t-test) showed that the values for tcount and ttable were 5.53 and 1.699, meaning $t_{count} < t_{table}$ so that H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. It can be concluded that there is an influence of the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) cooperative learning model on student learning outcomes . class IV on the sub-theme "Benefits of Energy" at SD Negeri 096113 Tanjung Saribu. Thus, the pretest and posttest have the same variance so that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, so the t-test in the research class that uses the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) type cooperative learning model is more influential.

The Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) Learning Model on the Learning Outcomes of Class V Students Subtheme 1 How the Body Processes Food at State Elementary School NO 125138 Pematang Siantar"

THEORETICAL REVIEW

To see the influence of the Savi learning model on student learning outcomes, a test was carried out. There are two tests given, namely pretest and posttest . In the initial test, a pretest was given , namely before the treatment was carried out, namely a multiple choice test with a total of 25 questions. In the next lesson, treatment was carried out by applying the Savi learning model. Next, a final test was given, after being given treatment, they were given a multiple choice test with a total of 25 questions. After the pretest and posttest results are obtained, the difference is looked for, where this difference will be used as a reference to determine the effect of the Savi learning model on student learning outcomes. From the treatment given, it is hoped that there will be a significant influence on student learning outcomes in subtheme 3 ways to maintain the health of human circulatory organs in class V SDN 091608 Sinaksak T.A 2023/2024.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODS

This research was carried out at SD Negeri 125138 which is located at Jalan Medan Simpang Kerang, Sumber Jaya 1 Village, Pematang Siantar City in the odd semester of the 2023/2024 academic year. This study uses a quantitative approach. This research uses an experimental method with a Pre Experimental Design research design using One Group Pre-test Post-test . This research design only involved one class by providing a pre-test and post-test . The population of this study was all fifth grade students at SD Negeri 125138, consisting of one class totaling 38 students. The sampling technique in this research is Total Sampling , so the sample in this research is the total number of class V, totaling 38 students.

One Group Pretest Post Test Research Design

Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
O1	X	O2

The data collected in this research are the results of class V students' learning for Subtheme 1 How does the body process food? The data collection technique in this research is a test in the form of multiple choice questions. To determine whether the instrument items are suitable to be given, instrument validation is first carried out. The test results that have been tested are then given to the experimental class. The data analysis technique used to test the research hypothesis is the t test. Before the t test is carried out, a prerequisite test is first carried out , namely a normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov formula and a homogeneity test using the sample test formula t test and Anova

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

The results of research using the Student Teams Achievement Division learning model are applied so that students work together with each other, have the ability to take responsibility for the results of group work, are able to unite their thoughts and ideas, students are more courageous, train students to share knowledge. In this way, each student will develop a sense of positive

dependence so that this will influence the learning outcomes of class V students. Subtheme 1 How does the body process food? . Viewed in terms of grades, it shows that there are differences in the learning outcomes of class V students after being treated with the Student Teams Achievement Division learning model . The pretest results obtained an average of 48.84 . After being given treatment, the average posttest result was 85.36 .

Before the hypothesis test is carried out, prerequisite tests are carried out, namely the normality test and homogeneity test. Based on the data normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov formula which is presented in the following table.

Table 1 . Normality Test Results

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		
	Statistics	df	Sig.
Pre-Test	.126	38	.133
Post-Test	.111	38	.200 *

From table 1, the normality test results obtained a significance in the pretest of 0.133 and a significance in the posttest of 0.200 with a sample of 38 students. Judging from the results of decision making, it can be concluded that the pretest and posttest data are normally distributed because the significance results obtained are > 0.05 .

Next, homogeneity testing was carried out. Based on the data homogeneity test, it is used to find out whether several population variants are the same or not. This test was carried out as a requirement in the independent sample t test and Anova analysis which is presented in the following table.

**Table 2 . Homogeneity Test Results
Homogeneity Test**

Test of Homogeneity of Variances			
Learning outcomes			
Levene Statistics	df1	df2	Sig.
.060	1	74	.806

Data from table 2 obtained a significance value of 0.806 . Based on the basis of homogeneity test decision making, it can be concluded that the data is homogeneous where $0.806 > 0.05$.

After the prerequisite tests are carried out, the t test analysis is carried out. A summary of the results of the t test analysis is presented in the following table.

Table 3. t test results

Table 4. 9 Homogeneity Tests

Paired Samples Test

Paired Differences	t	Df	Si
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	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig(2-tailed)	
				Lower	Upper				
Pair 1	PostTest – PreTest	36.211	12.016	1.949	32.261	40.160	18.576	37	.000

Based on table 4.13 above, it is found that $t = 18.576$ with a significant level (2-tailed) of 0.000, with a significant probability of $t = 18.576 > 2.026$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the Student Teams Achievement Division Learning Model on learning outcomes for theme 3 subtheme 1 How the Body Processes Food for Class V SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar.

Discussion

Based on the pretest results, the average value of student learning outcomes was 48.84 with all students scoring below the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using the Influence of the Student Teams Achievement Division Learning Model was relatively low. Furthermore, the average value of the posttest results was 85.37. So after using the Student Teams Achievement Division Learning Model, students have better learning outcomes than before using the Student Teams Achievement Division Learning Model. After the pretest and posttest normality tests were carried out, a homogeneity test was carried out. Based on the homogeneity test, a significant value of 0.931 was obtained. Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the value obtained is $t > t$ table ($t = 18, 576 > t$ table = 2.026) and the significance is $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an influence of the Student Teams Achievement Division learning model on the learning outcomes of Subtheme 1, how the body processes food for class V students at SD Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar. This is also supported by researchers Eduard, et al (2022) who in their research said that there was a significant influence of the Student Teams Achievement Division learning model on students' Energy Benefits Subtheme learning outcomes supported by test results (t count of $5.53 = < 0.05$). It was concluded that the Student Teams Achievement Division learning model influenced the learning outcomes of Subtheme 1, how the body processes food in students' Indonesian and science learning.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The Student Teams Achievement Division learning model on the learning outcomes of class V Subtheme 1 How the Body Processes Food at SD

Negeri 125138 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year. Learning with the Student Teams Achievement Division makes students more active in the learning process.

Recommendations

From the results of observations and analysis, researchers provide several suggestions as follows:

1. From the results of observations and analysis, researchers provide several suggestions as follows: For schools , schools should pay more attention to student learning outcomes in order to improve the quality of education, especially at UPTD SD Negeri 122371 Pematang Siantar. For teachers , teachers should be more selective in choosing learning media that emphasizes students being more active and enthusiastic about learning. For researchers , researchers are expected to be able to develop monopoly game media by applying other materials to find out whether other materials are suitable for using the monopoly game media. For Researchers , Next For future researchers who want to apply the influence of the Student Teams Achievement Division Learning Model on results so that they can further develop and strengthen the Student Teams Achievement Division Learning Model so that the model can spread and teachers are interested in using it Student Teams Achievement Division Learning Model .

REFERENCES

- Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2019. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2020. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Abduloh., dkk. 2019. *Peningkatan dan Pengembangan Prestasi Belajar Peserta Didik*. Jawa Timur: Uwais Inspirasi Indonesia.
- Andi, Arsana, Jampel, & Kusmariyatni, 2017 *Model STAD Berpengaruh Terhadap Sikap Sosial dan Hasil Belajar IPA*. *Jurnal Penelitian dan Pengembangan Pendidikan*. Vol. 4 (3). 351-361.
- Dedek Andrian et al., 2020. *Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe Student Team Achievement Division terhadap Hasil Belajar pada Sub Tema Manfaat Energi di Kelas IV SD Negeri 096113 Tanjung Saribu T.A 2022/2023*. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Konseling*. Vol 4, No 5, Tahun 2022.
- Istarani. 2011. *58 Model Pembelajaran Inovatif*. Medan : Media Persada.
- Kurniawan 2011:13 *Peningkatan dan Pengembangan Prestasi Belajar Peserta Didik*. Jawa Timur: Uwais Inspirasi Indonesia.

- Kusumastuti 2018. Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Koopertife Tipe STAD Terhadap Hasil Belajar Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Penelitian dan PKM Bidang Ilmu Pendidikan*. Vol 2, No 2, Maret 2021, (108-113).
- Setiawan Eko. 2018. *Pembelajaran Tematik Teoritis & Praktis*. Jakarta: Esensi Erlanga.
- Saefuddin & Berdiati 2014. Model Pembelajaran dan Implementasi Pendidikan HAM Dalam Prespektif Pendidikan Islam dan Pendidikan Nasional. *Relaj: Religion Education Social Laa Raiba Journal*. Vol 4, No 1, (2022) 133-144.
- Setiawan, M. Andi. 2017. *Belajar dan Pembelajaran*. Yogyakarta: Bandung. PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Slavin 2013. Penerapan Model Pembelajaran Kooperatif Tipe STAD Untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar IPA. *Jurnal Ilmiah Sekolah Dasar*. Vol.1 (1) 1-8.
- Sugiyono 2017. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. bandung : Alfabeta,cv.
- Suharsimi Arikunto 2019 *Prosedur Penelitian, Sautu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: PT RINEKA CIPTA.
- Tiga ranah Taksonomi BLOOM Dalam Pendidikan. *Jurnal Edukasi dan Sains*. Vol 2, No 1, Juni 2020; 132-139.
- Wahab 2015:243. *Peningkatan dan Pengembangan Prestasi Belajar Peserta Didik*. Jawa Timur: Uwais Inspirasi Indonesia.